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Impact of Remittances on Poverty Levels in Mexico

Carlos Encinas-Ferrer¹, David Martínez-Mendizabal², Eddie Villegas-Zermeño³

¹ Universidad del Valle de Atemajac (UNIVA)

^{2,3} Universidad Iberoamericana León

Abstract

In this research, the authors analyze the behavior of the economy in Mexico during the years in which neoliberal ideas have dominated government policies and their relationship with poverty and migration. The study of the evolution of the growth of the real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) shows that from 1980 there is a significant fall in its annual performance, but even more if we observe how the real GDP per capita evolves, the one that would translate into better living conditions and does not get to improve the standard of living of the great majorities. The lack of growth in real income per inhabitant has not only translated into poverty but has been accompanied by a high concentration of income in a small percentage of the richest people in the country, and it has become a real poverty trap for Mexico. Our working hypothesis is that the variations in the levels of poverty have been due in a greater extent to the increasing income of remittances than to the assistance programs established by the government of our country.

Keywords: Real GDP Per Capita, Poverty, Remittances

1. Introduction

The president of Mexico, Andrés Manuel López Obrador (AMLO), has pointed out as one of the central plans of his administration (2018-2024) the combat of the causes that originate migration, which are found in the lack of development not only in Mexico, but also in the Central American countries, as the migratory problems of this region have shown us recently. For this purpose, AMLO has proposed to the US and Canada governments a regional plan that encourages economic growth and roots of the population in their countries.

From this perspective, the actual government of our country focuses on the migratory problem not only on poverty but on the lack of employment and opportunities in their localities of residence.

About the above, Sánchez Ruiz (2010) points out that in the rural population of our country from those in extreme poverty only 15% of the total receives remittances, while in those that are in multidimensional poverty, 52.3% receive them. This would imply that migration to the US would be lower in extreme poverty levels. since the costs of carrying it out would be too high for them and this may be one of the many reasons that would have prevented to reduce its percentage at the national level.

2. Economy, income and remittances: factors to understand Mexican migration.

Undoubtedly, the lack of growth that our country shows have occurred since the establishment of the neoliberal model and the commercial opening in our country.

In the next table, we see the above mentioned with statistical clarity. During the time studied, average annual growth in constant 2013 pesos was 3.14%, but when looking for real growth per inhabitant, the annual average falls to 1%, and if it is maintained, it will take 70 years to double the current one (\$ 140,503 pesos per year, \$ 11,709 pesos monthly per capita) being quite low.

Table 1
Mexico: Real Gross Domestic Product and real Gross Domestic Product per capita

Date	Real GDP (millions of pesos base year 2013=100)	Real GDP per capita (Thousands of pesos, year base 2013=100)
1993	10,165,571.2	112,202
1994	10,667,860.3	115,517
1995	9,996,720.6	106,297
1996	10,673,824.3	111,549
1997	11,404,645.3	117,233
1998	11,993,572.6	121,366
1999	12,323,822.1	122,869
2000	12,932,921.4	127,143
2001	12,880,621.9	124,973
2002	12,875,489.7	123,381
2003	13,061,718.5	123,643
2004	13,573,815.1	126,863
2005	13,887,072.5	128,024
2006	14,511,307.2	131,810
2007	14,843,826.0	132,728
2008	15,013,577.7	132,090
2009	14,219,998.4	123,111
2010	14,947,794.7	127,412
2011	15,495,333.6	130,114
2012	16,059,723.7	132,914
2013	16,277,187.1	132,836
2014	16,733,654.8	134,708
2015	17,283,855.9	137,292
2016	17,784,717.8	139,444
2017	18,147,787.5	140,503

(Source: own elaboration with data from Banco de México and the World Bank)

The performance of our economy measured by the sexennial government periods studied has been truly poor and has limited our capacity for real growth. Let's see it in the following table.

Table 2
Performance of real GDP growth per capita as a six-year governmental period average

Period	The average annual rate of economic growth	Years needed to double GDP per capita
1995-2000	1.7162%	41
2001-2006	0.6181%	113
2007-2012	0.1973%	355
2013-2017	1.1259%	62

(Source: own elaboration with data from Banco de México and the World Bank)

At 2017 prices, the GDP reached \$ 21,785,270.7 million pesos, which gives us \$ 14,055.38 pesos per capita per month. When multiplying this amount by an average family of 4.5 members, we would have an average monthly income of \$ 63,247 pesos per family, which is not a poverty income at all. This leads us to another problem in our country: the high concentration of income in a small percentage of the total of its inhabitants (Carlos Encinas-Ferrer, 2017). It is important to emphasize that the rate of accumulation in the upper economic spheres of the Mexican population is much greater than the low growth of GDP (21.5% versus 7.1% in 2017, measured in dollars at current prices according to data from Banco de México. La Jornada 2018), which implies that this increase of almost 15% is based on a zero-sum game in which what some earn others lose.

The rapid increase in economic inequality and the small increase in real GDP per capita constitutes a serious obstacle both to the eradication of poverty and to the distribution of prosperity so that poor people can benefit from it.

Extreme inequality undermines economic growth and the ability of a country to reduce poverty; it limits the possibilities of living without exceeding the planet's resources and winning the war against climate change and makes the struggle in favor of gender equality very difficult.

As Joseph Stiglitz (2014) points out: "The extreme inequality in terms of income and wealth that currently exists in much of the world is detrimental to our economy and our society and undermines our policy. Although this situation should concern all of us, it is certain that it is the poorest people who suffer the most: not only are their lives affected by great inequality, but they also lack, to a large extent, equal opportunities. The Oxfam report reminds us, at a very opportune moment, that any initiative that really seeks to eradicate poverty must face decisions about public policies that generate and perpetuate inequality."

The phenomenon of income concentration is general, and it is taking place at a global, regional and national level. Its beginning coincides with the domain of neoliberal economics since 1980 and the implementation of its two main measures:

a: dismantling the Welfare State

b: global commercial and financial opening.

In the case of Mexico, we have seen several works in which the issue of inequality is addressed but clearly focused on its relationship with poverty. We can highlight, among others, the studies carried out periodically by the National Council for the Evaluation of Social Development Policy (CONEVAL, 2010). This body measures different dimensions to calculate poverty:

1. The poverty of minimum well-being - monthly income per family member of at least \$ 1,242.61 pesos in the urban environment and \$ 868.25 in rural areas;
2. Poverty of welfare - 2,542.13 pesos (urban) and 1,614.65 (rural).
3. Other - social deficiencies in education, access to health services, access to social security, access to food, quality, and housing space, and basic housing services.

Many investigators are studying the problem of income concentration and its relationship with poverty: Gerardo Esquivel (2015) made, under the sponsorship of Oxfam Mexico, the important work "Extreme Inequality in Mexico" and Araceli Damian with Julio Boltvinik (2015) presented their work "Evolution of poverty and social stratification in Mexico 2012-2014. Method of Integrated Measurement of Poverty and Social Stratification (MMIPE)"

Figure 1
Mexico: GDP share of capital and labor

Source: Own elaboration with data from INEGI.

Income concentration is related to low wages. In Figure 1 as of 1993, we observe the way in which the proportion of GDP that corresponds to work reduces while that of capital widens. Obviously here we have the origin of the accumulation of income and the fall of the capacity of the domestic market to become the dynamic element of our economy.

Figure 2
Evolution of productivity and remunerations in dollars (Index Base year 2008)

Source: own elaboration with INEGI data.

Figure 3 shows us better than none the problem that implies the concentration of income in our country. But the problem is even more serious. If we analyze that 90% of the population of our country that has an annual per capita income of \$ 4,271 dollars and that represents 120 million people, we will find that 65 million of them, 72%, have a monthly income per person less than \$ 2,000 per year and, therefore, are below the so-called

welfare poverty line and 39 million, 33% of those 120 million people, are below the minimum poverty threshold, 33%.

Figure 3
Distribution of annual income between 90%, 9% and 1% of the population in Mexico (US\$ nominal prices)

Source: own elaboration with data of INEGI 2014.

2.2. The welfare and malaise regime as a context of Mexican migrations.

The critical theory of undocumented migrations stresses a set of structural factors typical of advanced global capitalism that cause the temporary or definitive separation of large groups of the population from their original localities, accompanied by suffering and uncertainty as migration phenomena, largely measure, are associated with other types of expulsions such as poverty and depredation of the environment. Sassen (2014) assigns a special meaning to the concept of expulsion. It links it to a wild selection and to new logics that disrupt old processes; the concept "takes us beyond the more familiar idea of increasing inequality as a way of referring to the pathologies of global capitalism today ... they are not spontaneous but made. The instruments range from elementary policies to complex institutions, techniques, and systems ... with intricate institutional formats" (pp. 12 and 13).

Indeed, it seems that the risk detected by Santos (2010) of "preventing the market economy from extending its scope to transforming society into a market society" (p.152) appears as a tangible reality and is expressed in our individualized and individualized society, present in the migratory expulsions that will not be resolved by "encircling walls ... no side of wars between them and we can hope that victory will allow us to recover their much-desired security" (Bauman, 2011).

The collective exodus in poverty condition is the result of a complex set of dynamic interactions and not necessarily attributable to what was advised by traditional analyzes, mono or bi causal, which indicated their origin in wars and armed conflicts, by droughts and crises in the production of food, by the living conditions linked to different forms of poverty and social deprivation or by a simple combination of these factors. Processes characteristic of civilizational change and that lie well below the most superficial factors could give accurate explanations, which would perhaps bring a different understanding of the possible, feasible alternatives to understand the phenomenon:

We are witnessing the construction not so much of predatory elites as of predatory "formations," a combination of elites and systemic capabilities with finance as a key enabler, which presses towards acute concentration. The

concentration at the top is nothing new. What worries me are the extreme forms today in more and more fields in a good part of the world (Sassen, 2014, p.24).

As proposed by Held and McGrew (2003, p.13), globalized capitalism has excluded and expelled a large part of the population from its benefits and is, therefore, a deeply divisive process. For Mexico, these affirmations are subscribed in their entirety, as a faithful witness to the old phenomenon of recycled migration from the new inequalities that have brought forty years of economic, political and cultural restructuring in this stage called post-neoliberal. One of the indicators to assess the magnitude of the problem is the analysis of the poverty trajectory in the country, a fundamental factor, within this complex society, to understand the status of undocumented migration.

Social fractures involve a violation of human rights and are directly related to the active spheres constituting welfare regimes (Esping Andersen, 2000), which, even recognizing the neoliberal context shared since the 1980s in Latin America, are shaped national and sub-national differentiated problems. The theory of the welfare regime helps to look more extensively and complex at the tensions of contemporary societies (Morin, 2011). Taylor-Gooby defines the welfare regime as "a constellation of social, political and economic arrangements that tend to feed a particular welfare system, which in turn supports a pattern of social stratification (cited by Barba, 2006, p.97)".

Arrangements or combinations of structures generate a complex dynamic that provides conditions for the violation or to access to human rights: the dynamics of the labor market and income, the role of the State in the structuring of public policies with a particular notion of equality and the cultural dimension that produces and reproduces different ideological forms, which in general justify and normalize the inequality between sexes, races and social classes. When social arrangements cause inequality, we refer to it generally as structural violence.

As Carlos Barba says it is worth investigating:

The different ways in which the economy, the government and the domestic sphere have been historically articulated to determine who gets well and who are excluded, as well as to explore how welfare is achieved and why some do not have access to it. The intention is to explain the forces that, in addition to the market, have shaped the social structures of the countries (Barba, 2006, p 253).

The relationship between the supranational, national and subnational must be understood from a recursive and dynamic logic and not as cause and effect, that is, an accurate analysis would have to consider, in addition to the macrostructural factors, the forms of struggle for power and dimensions of organization and awareness that originate in the different areas. In this way, Mexico will be seen as a multiscale configuration of realities with their own traits -from below- and not as one-dimensional effects of the national dynamics -from above-, although the membership of a civilizer project guided by neoliberal keys is shared.

In societies such as Mexico, which brings together old and new inequalities, the macro-structural challenges facing the country are multiple, but perhaps, as a starting point, the following could be considered: an inflation that by 2017 represents the highest in 20 years and a growth of around 2% of GDP - much lower than official projections - almost 6 out of 10 workers are in informality, wages are precarious, and 1% of the population accumulates 23% of income; major problems both for coverage and quality in education, health, and housing; the percentage of the population that experiences poverty by income has not been able to be diminished in a period of 20 years, 53.4 million people are poor and what could represent a synthesis of varied and serious problems only 27.8% of the population is not poor and not vulnerable (they have their social rights covered in some way) and an unsustainable conception of development (CONEVAL, 2016, 2017); an unprecedented situation of insecurity and violence -especially in fraudulent homicides and femicides-, an overburdened justice system and levels of corruption - valued at 86 billion dollars (Casar, 2015) - and intolerable impunity.

For this article, it is worth noting that, since the middle of the first decade of the 21st century, efforts were strengthened in the Mexican government to understand and measure poverty, a task that had been carried out in different institutions research.

The General Law of Social Development (LGDS) of 2004 establishes the creation of the National Council for the Evaluation of Social Policy (CONEVAL) with a twofold purpose: to measure the trajectory of poverty in

Mexico, evaluate the social development policy and establish suggestions on the modifications that must be made in public policy to address social lags. In Chapter VI of the LGDS, Article 36, states that for the definition, identification, and measurement of poverty at least the following indicators will be used: I. Current income per capita; II. Average educational lag in the home; III. Access to health services; IV. Access to social security; V. Housing quality and spaces; VI. Access to basic services in the housing; VII. Access to food, and VIII. The degree of social cohesion. The way of measuring poverty has not been exempted from discussions, be it about the measurement methodology, about the weight of each of the indicators in the global poverty index or about the recommendations to modify the current state of things.

The CONEVAL reports every two years since 2010, the trajectory of poverty at the national and federal levels and every five years for the municipalities. Of the various instruments that are available, there are two that are important to present the general panorama of Mexico on poverty: multidimensional poverty and income poverty. The results are shown below:

Table 3
Evolution of poverty in Mexico and Guanajuato. Percentage.

	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016
Guanajuato	44.1	48.5	44.5	46.6	42.4
México	44.4	46.1	45.5	46.2	43.6

Source: CONEVAL (2017). Poverty results in Mexico at the national level and by states 2008-2016.

Table 4
The number of people living in poverty in Mexico and Guanajuato in thousands.

	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016
Guanajuato	2,403.60	2,703.70	2,525.80	2,683.30	2,489.70
México	49,489.50	52,813.00	53,349.90	55,341.60	53,418.20

Source: CONEVAL (2017). Poverty results in Mexico at the national level and by states 2008-2016.

As CONEVAL (2017) declares, and in accordance with the previous graphs, at a national level:

Between 2008 and 2016, poverty increased by 3.9 million people; at the same time, 2.9 million people stopped being in extreme poverty. This is the result, on the one hand, of the reduction of most of the social deprivations, although the lack of access to social security and food is still high and, on the other hand, the income of households has had an erratic history (p.3).

And continues:

At the household level, although the purchasing power of labor income increased 8.6% between 2014 and 2016, it fell by 10.6% between 2005 and 2017. This is compounded by the recent inflation increase, which in 2017 reached 6.77% percent, has caused a decrease in the purchasing power of households of 2.5% in that year. In addition to the above, the inequality in the distribution of income has remained high, and no economic factors have been observed, such as an improvement in productivity, that allow us to assume a change in this trend (p.3).

For Guanajuato, according to the tables shown above, achievements have been scarce. Although poverty fell from 1.7% in 2008-2016, this implied an absolute increase of 86,000 people more in poverty. The hypothesis that lies at the base of this document is that although extreme poverty decreased, this is mainly due to remittances sent to Guanajuato from abroad.

According to the analysis of the behavior of the factors that make up poverty measured in a multidimensional way, it can be argued that there are advances in several of them, such as schooling and health coverage, but others are stagnating or going backward. Consistently, the income factor is the one that has prevented the best results in terms of combating poverty. In fact, the CONEVAL, in all its evaluations, has called attention to the

existence of transversal public policies so that the economic strategy does not move to the parallel of the social strategy.

The following graphs show the seriousness of the problem.

Figure 4
Evolution of the population in poverty in terms of income for Mexico. 1992-2016.
(Millions of people).

Source: CONEVAL (2017). Measuring poverty in Mexico and the Federative Entities 2016

Figure 5
Evolution of the population in poverty in terms of income for Guanajuato. 1990-2014 (Percentage of Total).

Source: GUANAJUATO. Pobreza estatal 2016. (CONEVAL 2017).

That is why in his most recent evaluation he says:

Meanwhile, the income composition of the country's poorest population is still dependent on government transfers and remittances. This composition weakens the income in front of eventualities since these supports do not have a mandatory character ... probably, the most urgent income situation continues to be the inequality in its distribution ... the effects of the inequality in the distribution of income could derive in disadvantages that persist and are strengthened throughout the life cycle, reproducing, as in the case of poverty, in an intergenerational way (CONEVAL, 2018, p.15).

CONEVAL proposes the increase of the income of the population in conditions of poverty conditioned to the promotion of strategies to raise productivity or to the redistribution of income through taxation. This proposal, limited but politically correct, requires a detailed analysis, which is presented in the following section.

3. Statistical and econometric analysis.

From the data available in the last 20 years, measured in biannual periods, we find the relationship between Remittances and Non-Poverty (Defined not as welfare, but as belonging to the lower limit of the absence of poverty, which allows us to know the impact of remittances on poverty.).

Those data are the following:

Table 5. The relationship between Remittances and Non-Poverty

Period	Remittances (MD)	Non-poverty (%)
1995-1996	\$7,896.41	31.0
1997-1998	\$10,491.69	36.3
1999-2000	\$12,482.30	46.4
2001-2002	\$18,709.71	50.0
2003-2004	\$33,470.43	52.8
2005-2006	\$47,255.11	57.1
2007-2008	\$51,203.80	52.2
2009-2010	\$42,610.21	48.9
2011-2012	\$45,241.29	47.7
2013-2014	\$45,950.03	46.8
2015-2016	\$51,778.05	49.8

Remittances are measured in thousands of dollars, while non-poverty is measured as a percentage of the total population. Graphically, this relationship is observed as follows:

Figure 6. Mexico: Remittances and Non-Poverty

Source: Own elaboration with data from Banco de Mexico and INEGI.

To the naked eye, the relationship between remittances and non-poverty is closely related since the behavior is very similar. When remittances go up, poverty is reduced, or non-poverty rises, when remittances go down, poverty goes up.

Finding a regression equation in which we define remittances as the cause, and non-poverty as an effect, we have the following set of equations:

$$NP = 37.04 + 0.000304R$$

$$P - VALUE = 0.0137$$

$$R^2 = 0.51$$

$$DW = 0.59$$

We can see, from the results obtained, that there is a direct relationship between remittances and non-poverty as we define this concept. Since non-poverty is expressed as a percentage, the marginal rate of substitution between remittances and non-poverty is 0.0003% per thousand dollars of remittances. In other words, the entry of one thousand dollars in remittances lowers poverty by 0.0003%. Since the p-value is 0.0137, we conclude that it is significant at 95% confidence. The coefficient of determination is 51%, this is a remarkable value since it means that 51% of those people in the lower limit of welfare in the country is explained by the remittances, which is a very important percentage. Although the Durbin-Watson is 0.59 and this speaks to positive autocorrelation, which is logical, we need more variables to explain the reduction of poverty in the country in that period. Variables such as social spending, direct or indirect foreign investment, and others, should be included; but more than half explained by remittances is a huge amount.

Conclusions

The prevalence of poverty in Mexico, which coexists with marginal decreases of some specific poverties such as education, health, and housing, is mainly explained by the lack of income of the population, in the context of an unequal appropriation of wealth sharpened during the neoliberal period.

Despite the need to carry out studies that incorporate more variables to the model that has been presented in this article such as social spending and direct and indirect investment, the hypothesis that is part of it is proven because there is a high positive correlation between non-poverty and remittances.

The results of this research coincide with the evaluations of CONEVAL, in the sense of promoting, in the same direction and with a human rights approach, economic policy, and social policy, which until now have remained with different logics and at a certain level contradictory.

Not all remittances reach the poorest households, but it is necessary to consider at a fair level the contribution that is made from abroad by the migrant families themselves because without their contribution the levels of poverty that the country would reach would be much more scandalous than those reported until today. Remittances have served as a floor that prevents further collapse of the living standards of the marginalized population.

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